

A double blind, placebo-controlled trial investigating the efficacy of Pet Remedy on stress responses seen during handling in captive reptiles

Grace Bell FHEA, PGDip, PGCE, MSc, BSc (Hons) ^a

Angela Jowett BSc (Hons) ^a

^aDN Colleges, The Hub, Chappell Dr, Doncaster DN1 2RF

August 2024

Abstract

Reptiles are increasingly becoming popular as exotic pets. There are increasing issues with the public misinterpreting reptilian behavioural welfare indicators when handling as being the norm. With many reptiles demonstrating fear and stress responses when handled. Pet Remedy™ is a herbal product containing valerian, marketed as a calming aid. Its influence on reptilian behaviour and physiology has been previously untested. We designed a randomised, double blind, placebo-controlled trial into the effectiveness of Pet Remedy on different reptiles. Thirty-seven reptiles underwent a baseline measure, a placebo treatment, a Pet Remedy treatment and a control measure. We measured reptile behaviour and breathing rate within the home vivarium and when being handled by the same handler for all components. Exposure to Pet Remedy was associated with a significant reduction in stress behaviours observed during handling ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in breathing rates with the administration of Pet Remedy vs the in vivarium breathing rates in reptiles ($F = 2.44, p < 0.05$). The results of this study demonstrate the need for further investigation into the influence of valerian-based pharmaceuticals on the behaviour and physiology of captive reptiles to promote positive welfare.

Introduction and Literature Review

Reptiles have become increasingly popular exotic pets in the UK and across the world, with an estimated 5% of UK homes housing reptiles as pets, (an increase from 3.4% in 2022) (Valdez, 2021; Gupta, 2023). Reptiles are growing increasingly popular in collections; public, private and educational, regardless of this popularity, there has been little information gathered into the ability of reptile owners to meet the needs of their reptiles. Azevedo *et al.* (2021) investigated 220 pet reptile owners and 85% of respondents failed to provide at least one of the four husbandry needs. In addition there was a significant number of respondents who incorrectly interpreted behaviours, indicative of poor welfare and captivity stress were considered 'normal' by some respondents (Azevedo *et al.* 2021). There has historically been a lack of research into the behavioural and physiological indicators of reptiles regarding their welfare. Previous research might suggest that poor welfare and abnormal behaviours in pet reptiles have become accepted as normal. Thus, justifying the search for ways to prevent them. These results suggest that campaigns aimed at challenging the predominant view, propelled by the exotic pet industry, that reptiles are low-maintenance pets needs to be actively refuted.

Preventing stress during husbandry practices, e.g. health checks, routine vet visits and vivarium management, needs to be attempted to ensure the promotion of adequate welfare in reptiles (Gangloff and Greenberg, 2023). Coupled with this ideally there should also be a push within the industry to also promote positive welfare practices within reptile collections. Not only to meet the welfare needs of individuals but also to promote further cognitive welfare through positive human-reptile interactions when these interactions may be unavoidable. Chronic captive stress in reptiles, can increase illness incidence and increase the chances of mortality (O'Rourke and Lertpiriyapong, 2015). Some species also demonstrate severe biological functions when they find themselves within a high stress environment e.g. Geckos and tail autotomy and skin sloughing (Pafilis *et al.*, 2009). Changes in monoaminergic activity have been proved to be the result of a cascade of hormone release from the adrenal axis and have been demonstrated in a number of vertebrate species. Serotonergic systems have been demonstrated to be activated both rapidly and slowly following a stressful event (Emerson *et*

al. 2000). The biological mechanisms associated with both acute and chronic stress responses, can be manipulated through the use of biological pharmaceutical agents with proven success in mammals, but there has been limited research undertaken in reptile species (Unwin *et al.* 2020, Warwick *et al.* 2023).

Pet Remedy is an aerosol calming spray product marketed at alleviating stress responses in predominantly mammalian species. Pet Remedy's mode of action is to mimic Gamma Amino Butyric Acid, which plays a role in controlling nerve cell hyperactivity associated with fear, stress and anxiety. It also increases dopamine and serotonin production associated with a reduction in impulsive behaviour Maurer-Spurej (2005) evidenced that circulating serotonin can be found in the thrombocytes of some reptile species, predominantly those with endothermic properties but there was a lack of representation of exothermic reptilian species. Serotonin as a vasoactive substance, regulates skin blood flow, which is predominantly used in endothermic body temperature regulation.

Crews *et al.* (2009) speculated that there was a similar physiological process associated with the adrenal axis associated with stress in vertebrate species regardless of species. The mechanism of action therefore, should remain the same within reptiles when using Pet Remedy, comparable to that seen in mammals. Using products such as Pet Remedy, may reduce reptilian stress and fear during routine handling, which in turn will promote positive welfare within reptilian species.

Methods and Materials

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the UCNL ethics review board.

Subjects

Twenty-seven reptiles were sourced from two locations: 10 reptiles from an educational establishment in Doncaster and 17 from a reptile shop in Yorkshire. All testing was carried out in March – May 2024. Reptiles at the second location were handled minimally outside of the test procedures, the first location handled the animal as often as required to carry out daily husbandry checks. The reptiles were of varying species, not all individuals had been sexed prior to the study commencement due to minimal handling. Corn Snakes were the most common species ($n = 4$) with Milk Snakes ($n=3$) and Bearded Dragons ($n=3$) being the next most common, a total of 13 species were represented in the study, 17 were lizards and 10 were snake species. All individuals were housed in individual vivarium's meeting individual species requirements, all vivarium's had a Perspex or Glass door. All reptiles remained in the care of the establishment they were sourced from after completion of the study. Any individual with pre-existing illnesses were excluded from the study. All subjects had been in the location and their individual vivarium for at least a week.

Experimental Design

The study was of a within subjects design, each individual reptile was compared to itself due to the variation in species. Each subject was tested four times, each location has a single handler, this was carried out over a period of four days at each location. Baseline measures when observed in the vivarium with no handling were done on day 1, handling with no product applied was done on day 2, half the subjects were then randomly assigned to be exposed to either Pet Remedy and half to the placebo on the first experimental day, this would then swap

to the other product the next day. The experimenter and handler were blinded to which treatment was being used and these were applied on day 3 and day 4. For each cohort, on placebo bottle and one Pet Remedy bottle were used, with each bottle being labelled A and B respectively. The bottles were given to the experimenter and handler by an assistant to ensure they remained blind. The subjects were divided into two groups with half being tested in the morning and half being tested in the afternoon. This handling of the individuals took place in a single room and to avoid cross-contamination, all morning subjects were exposed to one product and all afternoon subjects were exposed to the other. When the morning group had been tested, the room was cleaned and the table which the reptiles were handled over was also cleaned. There was a 2-hour gap between recordings to ensure that the air had had chance to clear and recirculate. At this point the experimenter also changed their lab coat.

Experimental Procedure

In each of the testing centres, the testing area was in a room separate to the housing room, it was done out of sight and hearing of the other subject animals. A table was erected in the centre of the room in which the reptiles were to be handled, with a large tray placed over the top to discourage subjects from falling off the table. The experimenter obtained information from the centre managers prior to handling re the subjects willingness to be handled. The experimenter had made no contact with the animals before the start of the experiment. Each individual had a RAG rating system, Green, Amber, Red assigned to them from the centre managers in relation to their previous behaviour when handling. The experimenter wore a white long sleeved, knee length laboratory coat, and a face mask with tea tree oil to prevent distinction of the scent of Pet Remedy and the placebo. Before the start of testing on day 3 and 4, the appropriate product was applied to the experimenters' sleeves and coat, one spray was applied to each cuff and one spray to the body.

Testing Protocol

The subjects were tested for handling in the same order at each test centre at the same time each day over the four days and in the same order. Control measures were taken at opportune times during the day when individuals could be observed from outside the vivarium. Any individual that showed great aversion to handling would be withdrawn immediately; this did not occur during testing. Behaviours observed in the subjects were allocated to either positive or negative behaviour categories, with the number of behaviours observed in each category being given a score based on the number of behaviours observed (Table 1).

Table 1

Description of the behaviours observed allocated both positive and negative behaviours (Adapted from Warwick *et al.* 2013)

Positive Behaviours	Negative behaviours
Normal/relaxed alertness	Hyperactivity
Calm smelling or tasting objects or air	Hypoactivity
Unhurried body movements and locomotion and subtle body posture change	Excessive vocalisation e.g. hissing, pseudo vocalisation
Moderate or relaxed grasp on handler	Inflation of the body
Relaxed drinking or feeding	Human directed aggression
Relaxed breathing	Clutching the handler

Physical quiescence	Grating of jaw
	Species specific aversion e.g. loop pushing, pigmentation changes, tail autotomy, death feigning
	Cloacal evacuations
	Open mouth breathing

In Vivarium control measures

The experimenter approached each subject's individual vivarium and did not touch the vivarium door, if the subject was visible control measures of behaviour and breathing rate were recorded. If the subject was not visible, then the experimenter returned at a later point of day one to gather the control data.

Pickup

The experimenter opened the vivarium door and reached in to find the individual subject. Individuals sometimes were located without the need to move enclosure components, sometimes enclosure components had to be moved. The subject was then moved to the room with the table and tray, behaviours were recorded during this move. No individual took longer than a minute to move to the room from the vivarium.

Experimenter Handling

Following carrying the subject into the testing room. The experimenter spent the first minute undertaking a standard reptile health check. Following this the respiratory rate was recorded. Behaviour ratings were also done at this time. The number of escape attempts were also recorded. No animal was handled for longer than five minutes in total from the start of the experiment to returning to the vivarium.

Physiological Measures

The experimenter observed the chest cavity of each species to count the respiratory rate over 15 seconds and then converted this into breaths per minute. After completion of the experiment the subject was returned to their home vivarium. The experimenters disinfected their hands after each test with a non-scented antimicrobial hand gel. The tray and table were disinfected with a non-scented disinfectant after each subject test.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS 23. The assistant recorded breath rates per minute alongside the experimenter, this was analysed using an independent sample t-test to assess the interobserver reliability following completion of the tests. The assistant also recorded positive and negative behaviour frequencies during the testing components to assess interobserver reliability. A chi squared test for association analysis was undertaken to assess the impact of the different observers on behaviour scores awarded. We examined the effect of treatment (Pet Remedy and Placebo) and the order in which treatments were administered and the individual subjects baseline response and the interaction between the treatment type and the order applied.

Results

When the interobserver reliability was tested for behaviour scores and breaths per minute, both yielded no significant difference and demonstrated an agreement between observers ($p > 0.05$). The number of positive behaviours during handling was not significantly associated with the placebo treatment ($M = 1 \pm 1.41$), the pet remedy treatment ($M = 1 \pm 0.63$) or handling without any treatment ($M = 0.7 \pm 0.78$). More positive behaviours were significantly associated with presence in the vivarium ($M = 2.4 \pm 0.92$) rather than being handled ($X^2_3 = 1.05, p > 0.05$). The number of negative behaviours observed for placebo treatment ($M = 4.6 \pm 2.06$), the pet remedy treatment ($M = 3.1 \pm 1.81$) and the handling without any treatment ($M = 4.7 \pm 2.1$) all showed an increase in incidence and therefore behaviour score, related to handling compared to non-handling base line values ($M = 0.2 \pm 0.6$). There was a significant association relating to the treatment administered and the negative behaviour score, when this was investigated further, the administration of Pet Remedy significantly associated with the negative behaviour score ($X^2_3 = 0.69, p < 0.05$). Each individual subject was compared within subject's design due to the variation in species. Breath rate was increased during placebo treatment, handling without treatment and pet remedy treatment compared to base line values. There was a significant difference between the baseline breath rates and handling without treatment and placebo treatment ($F = 2.60, p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference between breathing rate between handling with Pet Remedy and baseline values ($F = 2.44, p < 0.05$). Both groups demonstrated more negative behaviours on the second day of testing ($M = 4.2 \pm 0.49$) vs the first day of testing ($M = 3.3 \pm 0.66$). Those subjects were exposed to Pet Remedy on the first day of testing demonstrated less attempts to escape and less negative behaviours on the second day than those subjects who received the placebo treatment first.

Discussion

The study, overall, did not see differences in the frequency of positive behaviours in reptile's dependent on whether the placebo, Pet Remedy or no treatment was administered when handling. The study did see a reduction in the negative behaviours observed during the administration of Pet Remedy comparable with baseline values compared to handling without Pet Remedy.

The aim of the research was to examine the impact of giving Pet Remedy to reptiles while they were being handled. The researchers specifically looked for positive behaviour variations between the reptiles receiving Pet Remedy, a placebo, or no treatment at all. The study found that when Pet Remedy was delivered, compared to handling without Pet Remedy, less negative behaviours were seen, even though no significant differences were found in positive behaviours. This shows that when reptiles interact with humans, Pet Remedy may have a calming impact on them. It is crucial to remember, nonetheless, that more investigation is required to completely comprehend Pet Remedy's therapeutic benefits for reptiles. Although research has highlighted recognised stress factors such as gecko tail autotomy and skin sloughing (Pafilis et al., 2009), it is apparent that limited relevant research has been undertaken when considering reptile stress factors in relation to the biological mechanisms in comparison to other species (Unwin et al. 2020, Warwick et al. 2023).

Through the use of pet remedy previously being proven as a natural calming product focusing on mimicking gamma amino butyric acid, investigating the effects of pet remedy as a treatment option within reptiles, to benefit health, is a critical element if proven successful in avoiding chronic stress consequences. The breathing rate of subjects was decreased when using pet remedy comparable with base line valued compared to no treatment or placebo treatment

application. In contrast Unwin *et al.* (2020) observed no concurrent significant change in respiratory rates in rabbits, in comparison a noticeable significant reduction in breathing rate was seen in reptiles. Breathing rates were relatively high throughout the study compared to previously recorded heart rates for the species in question. The high breath rates could be explained by the novel person undertaking the handling, and that several of the subjects were rated Amber and Red for handling regarding their previous behaviour. Breath rate was reduced by Pet Remedy administration, this would have been beneficial to link to heart rate in the subjects in terms of analysis of stress response. Due to the close link between breathing and heart rate, it could be expected that heart rate would mirror that of the breathing rates seen in subjects. Breathing rate could also have been due to the changes in environment when moving the reptile between experimental areas. It would be beneficial in the future to retest with a higher number of individuals and variety of species, who all have similar handling experience.

In summary, interobserver reliability for behaviour scores and breaths per minute showed no significant differences between observers ($p > 0.05$). Positive behaviours during handling were not significantly associated with treatments, but more positive behaviours were observed in the vivarium. Negative behaviours increased during handling, and Pet Remedy administration was linked to negative behaviour scores. Breath rate increased during treatments, and both groups exhibited more negative behaviours on the second day of testing. However, subjects exposed to Pet Remedy showed fewer escape attempts and negative behaviours on the second day compared to those who received the placebo initially

The method of administration of the current study was olfactory as opposed to topical or oral. This method was chosen due to the reliance on olfactory sensation within reptiles to interpret their environment (Carabajal *et al.* 2024). Due to the variation in scale morphology and the difference in permeability of the skin, topical application was not used to reduce the impact this variation may have. All individuals were chosen as they did not exhibit any signs of recent shedding, and none were due to shed close to the commencement of the study.

As previously emphasized by O'Rourke and Lertpiriyapong (2015), the ability to recognise stress responses are critical to a captive reptile with the potential of mortality being the result of chronic stress. As this study found less negative behaviours were observed after the use of pet remedy, this aligns with speculation stated by Crews *et al.*, (2009). Suggesting the mechanism of action of pet remedy to reduce reptilian stress when being handled. As previously highlighted, due to reptilian abnormal behaviours being disregarded, there are few comparable studies making the findings of this research relevant to support the use of pet remedy. With the aim to firstly recognise the presentation of stress, and subsequently reduce this within reptiles.

The purpose of double blind design eliminated any bias from the handler and the experimenter. Additionally a placebo control design was chosen for this study to reduce handler discrepancy and maintain consistency. The sample size within this study was vast and included a range of reptile species. Within this each subject was tested only against their own presentation with no multi reptile comparison included. This strengthens the study because this allows more accuracy whilst also accommodating each subjects individual handling experiences. With the studies results focusing solely on the specified days of observation. In addition the same handler was allocated to each location further adding to

consistency within the study. Furthermore, any animal exhibiting overly distressed behaviour at any stage during observation was immediately returned to its vivarium and eliminated from being included within this study, which promotes overall welfare of the animal as priority. Monitoring of the heart and breathing rates provide objective measures of stress levels within this study, strengthening the reliability of the results through the scientific factual basis that these tests provide. The observations of this study were subjective based with the experimenter being the only contributor to the data collected.

As this study was carried out over two locations with varying historical handling experience, this could be seen as a limitation to the consistency within the results. An additional limitation may be that the trial took place over a four day period which may have been distressing for animals with little previous handling encounters. Also mentioned within the study was the need to move items within the vivarium to locate the animal, this could have resulted in the animal experiencing initial distress prior to being transferred to the testing environment potentially implicating results. As discussed as a strength the same handler was used within each location however, there is no indication to the familiarity of the handler to the subjects prior to this study. Additionally, to further strengthen the results the same handler and experimenter across both locations would be beneficial. When considering sample size, 27 subjects were included of mixed reptilian species which allowed for diverse results. However, to improve future studies it would be suggested that more species-specific research was undertaken in the hope to increase correlation seen within results. As with any subjective measures in research there is the potential for bias, within this study the experimenter observed and recorded the behaviours presented based upon their own opinion of what was seen.

In regard to, the clinical application of Pet Remedy, there is a need for a greater level of analysis at a species level to investigate the effect it has on the reptiles behaviour and physiology. The integration of Pet Remedy into routine care practices to improve reptile welfare may improve welfare by other means. For example, the impact of Valerian based pharmaceuticals on mammals may see a calming effect in the handlers and owners when handling reptiles, something that may be considered when handling particularly flighty or dangerous individuals.

To further expand upon the limitations and potential bias previously discussed, it may be beneficial to future researchers to consider testing exact species to enable more species-specific results relating to the effects of pet remedy to be discovered. In addition, whether this is more effective in select species. Equally, consideration could be given to the age and sex of the species, which could enlighten whether these elements make a difference to results. Investigating previous handling history may also be beneficial, any previous unknown trauma which the animal has experienced may result in immediate stress when being handled, and could impact results, compared to other, non-traumatized subjects. Future researchers may also consider completing these tests over a different time scale, such as, once a week for several weeks to investigate whether consistent daily testing impacts behaviour, in comparison to handling less frequently over a longer period of time. To improve validity multiple observers would be beneficial to eliminate any bias results, moreover, repeating these tests through a test-retest model, would allow for investigation of long term effects of the use of pet remedy and allow for comparison, this would increase the reliability of results. Another recommendation would be to undertake this research across other captive species in order to provide a clearer understanding of the benefits of pet remedy overall and would lay

out a greater overview, further leading to the ability of comparison. A final suggestion for future researchers could include the administration of pet remedy in alternative ways, inclusive of applying pet remedy to an object within the vivarium prior to handling, allowing time for the product to enter the reptiles system.

Conclusions

An investigation into reptile behaviour before and following the administration Pet Remedy on routine handling procedures. Individual variation was demonstrated throughout the study dependent on species and individuals. High interobserver reliability was demonstrated. The study highlighted the high level of stress and fear behaviours within the captive reptile population. Pet Remedy used on a handler's clothing was associated with a significant association between breathing rates on both treated reptiles and baseline control values. Use of Pet Remedy was also associated with a decrease in negative stress behaviours demonstrated but no increase in positive captive behaviours being demonstrated. Through the differences in behaviour measures and the changes in breathing rate, there is a suggestion that the administration of Pet Remedy may have some influence and value for reptiles when being handled. Further investigation into the impact of Pet Remedy on the behaviour and physiology in reptiles is warranted.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Martyn Barklett-Judge, Managing Director of Unex Designs Ltd for providing products for the current study.

Conflict of Interest

The author's declare that none of them have competing interests.

Ethical considerations

None.

List of References

- Azevedo, Alexandre, Leonor Guimarães, Joel Ferraz, Martin Whiting, and Manuel Magalhães-Sant'Ana. 2021. "Pet Reptiles—Are We Meeting Their Needs?" *Animals* 11, 10. 2964. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11102964>
- Carabajal, A., Serres-Corral, P., Olvera-Maneu, S. and Lopexz-Bejar, M. 2024. Non-invasive measurement of glucocorticoids: The reptile perspective, *Journal of Zoology*, 232 (2), 87-96, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzo.13157>
- Crews, D., Sanderson, N. and Dias, B.G. 2009. Hormones, Brain and Behavior in Reptiles. *Elsevier*. Austin, TX, USA
- Gangloff, E. J. and Greenberg, N. 2023. Health and Welfare of Captive Reptiles. *Biology of stress*. 93-142. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86012-7_4
- Gupta, M. 2023. *Behind the Rise of the UK's Reptile Pet Population*. [Online]. Available from: <https://globalpetindustry.com/article/behind-rise-uks-reptile-pet-population>

Moore, T. and Jessop, T.S. 2003. Stress, reproduction and adrenocortical modulation in amphibians and reptiles, *Hormones and Behaviour*, 43 (1), 39-47, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0018-506X\(02\)00038-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0018-506X(02)00038-7)

O'Rourke, D. P. and Lertpiriyapong, K. 2015. Biology and Diseases of Reptiles. *Laboratory Animal Medicine*, 3, 967-1013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-409527-4.00019-5>

Pafilis, P., Foufopoulos, J., Poulakakis, N., Lymberakis, P. and Valakos, E. D. 2009. Tail Shedding in Island Lizards (Lacertidae, reptilia): Decline of Antipredator Defenses in Relaxed Predation Environments. *Evolution International Journal of Organic Evolution*. 63 (5), pp.1262-1278. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzo.13036>

Pet Remedy LTD. 2024. *How Pet Remedy Works*. [Online]. Available from : <https://petremedy.co.uk/how-it-works/#:~:text=Pet%20Remedy%20works%20with%20the%20pet%E2%80%99s%20own%20natural,getting%20a%20message%20from%20the%20brain%20to%20calm.> [Accessed 12 June 2024].

Unwin, S. L., Saunders R. A., Blackwell, E, and Rooney, N. J. 2020. A Double-Blind. Placebo-Controlled Trial Investigating the Value of Pet Remedy in Ameliorating Fear of Handling OF Companion Rabbits. *Journal of Veterinary Behaviour*. 36, 54-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jveb.2019.10.001>

Valdez, J. W. 2021. *Using Google Trends to Determine Current, Past, and Future Trends in Reptile Pet Trade*. *Animals*, 11 (3). doi: 10.3390/ani11030676

Warwick, C. 2019. *Reptilian Welfare in a Biological Context*. [Online] https://pure.port.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/21810086/UoP_PhD_Thesis_C_Warwick_FINAL.pdf

Warwick, C., Arena, P. C. and Burghardt, G. M. 2023. Health and Welfare of Captive Reptiles. 2nd ed. *Springer Charm*, Switzerland

Williams, J., & Beck, D. (2021). Stress, anxiety, fear and frustration in different reptile species: how to reduce these negative emotional states during veterinary procedures. *Veterinary Nursing Journal*, 36(7), 213–21 <https://doi.org/10.1080/17415349.2021.1936322>